

NUTRITION, BODY WEIGHT, AND PHYSICAL ACTIVITY: MODIFYABLE RISK FACTORS FOR DYSLIPIDEMIA AND METABOLIC SYNDROME IN GIRLS

Salomova Shakhinabonu Olimovna

PhD Researcher, Bukhara State Medical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17196826>

Puberty is a critical stage in the development of reproductive and metabolic health in girls. Along with hormonal changes, lifestyle determines how severe metabolic disorders will be. The main modifiable risk factors include poor nutrition, excess body weight, and lack of physical activity. Their impact on the lipid spectrum and metabolic syndrome in adolescence has been confirmed by numerous clinical studies [1.3.5.6].

Nutrition and its role in the formation of dyslipidemia

The diet of adolescent girls is often characterized by excessive consumption of simple carbohydrates, saturated fats and trans fats, and low fiber and protein content. Consumption of sugary soft drinks, fast food and snacks leads to hypertriglyceridemia and decreased levels of high-density lipoproteins. Lack of vegetables and fruits in the diet reduces the antioxidant potential of the body and promotes oxidative stress. stress[2.4].

Research shows that regular consumption of high glycemic index foods increases the risk of developing insulin resistance in adolescents by 25–30%. At the same time, the Mediterranean diet, rich in vegetables, fruits, fish and olive oil, is associated with improved lipid profiles and reduced body mass index[1.3].

Body weight and obesity as a risk factor

Overweight and obesity are the leading causes of metabolic disorders in adolescents. Visceral obesity in girls during puberty is accompanied by hyperinsulinemia, increased lipolysis and accumulation of free fatty acids, which leads to hypertriglyceridemia and increased LDL levels. According to large cohort studies, the risk of metabolic syndrome in obese girls is 4–5 times higher than in their peers with normal body weight [7.8].

The distribution of adipose tissue is of particular importance. Even with a moderate increase in body mass index, abdominal obesity significantly increases the likelihood of developing an atherogenic lipid profile.

Physical activity and prevention of metabolic disorders

Physical activity is one of the most effective ways to correct dyslipidemia . Regular aerobic exercise helps increase HDL levels, lower triglycerides, and reduce visceral fat. It has been established that 60 minutes of moderate or intense physical activity per day is enough to reduce the risk of metabolic syndrome by 25-40%.

However, modern teenage girls increasingly lead a sedentary lifestyle. The prevalence of physical inactivity among schoolgirls reaches 60–70%, which is aggravated by the long-term use of gadgets and a decrease in interest in sports [7].

Combined influence of factors

Nutrition, body weight and level of physical activity are interconnected and form a single set of risks. Girls with an unhealthy diet are more likely to develop obesity, which, in turn, reduces motivation for physical activity. As a result, a vicious circle is formed: unhealthy diet → obesity → insulin resistance → dyslipidemia → metabolic syndrome .

Table 1. Main modifiable risk factors for dyslipidemia and their impact on indicators in adolescent girls

Risk factor	Characteristic	Effect on lipid spectrum	Consequences
Excessive consumption of fats and sugar	Fast food , sugary drinks, trans fats	↑ TG, ↑ LDL, ↓ HDL	Hypertriglyceridemia , obesity
Lack of vegetables and fruits	Deficiency of fiber and antioxidants	↑ OX, ↑ oxidative stress	Early signs of atherosclerosis
Overweight	BMI > 85th percentile	↑ TG, ↑ LDL	Risk of metabolic syndrome ↑ 4-5 times
Abdominal obesity	Increased waist circumference	↑ FFA, ↑ VLDL, ↓ HDL	Insulin resistance , MS
Lack of physical activity	< 60 min/day	↓ HDL, ↑ TG	Increased atherogenicity of blood
Regular aerobic exercise	> 60 min/day	↑ HDL, ↓ TG	Reducing the risk of CVD and MS

It is also worth emphasizing that the influence of nutrition, body weight, and physical activity on the risk of dyslipidemia in girls during puberty is not only biochemical, but also social and behavioral. Modern studies show that adolescent girls are much more often exposed to advertising and trendy diets, which are often based on restricting individual nutrients but do not provide adequate nutrition. For example, low-carbohydrate or extremely low-calorie diets popular among adolescents can lead to a deficiency of protein, B vitamins, iron, and calcium. These deficiencies not only worsen overall well-being, but also aggravate metabolic imbalance, reducing the level of high-density lipoproteins and increasing the risk of hypertriglyceridemia.

Diet is of great importance. Skipping breakfast in adolescent girls is associated with a higher risk of obesity and metabolic syndrome. It has been established that regular three or four meals a day contribute to better control of glucose and lipid levels, while irregular meals and the habit of snacking on high-calorie foods between main meals increases the load on the pancreas and leads to hyperinsulinemia .

Physical activity, in turn, has a multifaceted effect. In addition to the direct effect on lipid metabolism and weight loss, regular exercise helps improve tissue sensitivity to insulin, reduce inflammatory markers, and increase antioxidant protection. Aerobic exercise (running, swimming, dancing, team sports) is considered particularly effective, but it is important to combine it with moderate strength training, which increases muscle mass and further increases the body's metabolic activity.

An important area of prevention is limiting sedentary behavior. Current data show that teenagers who spend more than 3-4 hours a day in front of a screen (phone, computer, TV) have a significantly higher body mass index and a worse lipid profile compared to their peers whose screen time does not exceed 2 hours. This is due not only to physical inactivity, but also to frequent snacks while using gadgets.

Psychological factors should not be forgotten either. Girls in puberty are particularly susceptible to stress associated with changes in figure and hormonal fluctuations. Chronic stress and lack of sleep affect the secretion of cortisol, which stimulates lipogenesis, increases

appetite and leads to the accumulation of visceral fat. Together, this increases the risk of insulin resistance and dyslipidemia.

Thus, comprehensive prevention of dyslipidemia and metabolic syndrome in girls should include not only dietary control and increased physical activity, but also work with psychological aspects, limiting sedentary behavior and forming correct eating habits with the participation of the family. Such a multi-level approach allows achieving sustainable results and reducing the risk of developing cardiovascular diseases in the future.

Conclusion. Modifiable risk factors - nutrition, body weight and physical activity level - play a key role in the formation of the lipid profile and metabolic syndrome in adolescent girls. Excessive calorie intake, obesity and physical inactivity contribute to the development of dyslipidemia and insulin resistance. In contrast, a balanced diet and regular physical activity are effective means of prevention.

Early diagnosis and correction of these factors can significantly reduce the prevalence of metabolic disorders and prevent cardiovascular diseases in the future.

Adabiyotlar, References, Литературы:

1. Cao J., Wang H., et al. Pubertal maturation and weight status are associated with dyslipidemia among Chinese adolescents // *Sci Rep* . - 2020. - Vol. 10. - Article 18069.
2. de Lamas C., Dafes C., et al. Progression of metabolic syndrome and associated cardiometabolic risk factors across puberty in adolescents // *Front Endocrinol* . - 2022. - Vol. 13. - Article 1082684.
3. Daniels SR, Pratt CA, Hayman LL Reduction of risk for cardiovascular disease in children and adolescents // *Circulation* . - 2011. - Vol. 124. - P. 1673-1686.
4. Reaven G. Insulin resistance: the link between obesity and cardiovascular disease // *Med Clin North Am* . - 2011. - Vol. 95, No. 5. - P. 875-892.
5. Vasyukova O.V., Grigorieva E.V., et al. Clinical guidelines: Obesity in children // *Obesity and metabolism* . - 2024. - 28 p.
6. Baranov A.A., Namazova -Baranova L.S., Zhukova E.V. Lipid disorders in children and adolescents: clinical significance // *Pediatrics* . - 2021. - Vol. 100, No. 5. - P. 48-53.
7. Tutelyan V.A., Kravtsova E.Yu. The role of nutrition in the formation of lipid spectrum disorders in adolescents // *Nutrition Issues* . - 2021. - Vol. 90, No. 3. - P. 48-55.
8. Sukhikh G.T., Prilepskaya V.N. Physical activity and metabolic health of adolescents // *Obstetrics, gynecology and reproduction* . - 2019. - Vol. 13, No. 3. - P. 35-41.
9. Rozhdestvenskaya N.B., Tkacheva O.N. Dyslipidemia and risk factors in adolescent girls // *Endocrinology* . - 2022. - Vol. 27, No. 4. - P. 41-47.